

Understanding the Cognitive Challenges of Non-GIS Experts - A Critical Step to Learn When Help is Needed in a Machine Guidance System

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1 Introduction

This research is motivated by a long-term goal of amplifying human capacity for doing geospatial analysis. We approach it by developing *machine guidance* that can actively help human analysts when they encounter cognitive difficulties in an analytical workflow. Geospatial analysis is a human-directed analytical process aimed at solving scientific or decision-making problems [9]. It depends on the use of GISystem and associated data representation, manipulation, statistical, and modeling methods to make sense of the phenomena underlying the geographic data [1, 10]. Such processes are challenging for people with limited training in geography and GISystem, and they impose high cognitive loads on the analysts.

Efforts to address the above challenges have taken by 1) empowering the users through developing education and training programs in geography and Geographic Information Science (GIScience) [7], and 2) improving the design of GISystem user interfaces to be more aligned with human spatial concepts [11]. However, educational programs are not scalable considering the cost of time and money. The improved system designs still burden users in forming suitable strategies, preparing data, and conducting required spatial functions.

We propose machine guidance [4] as an approach to support mixed-initiative geospatial analysis at scale. Machine guidance for geospatial analysis refers to the kind of machine intelligence that can recognize when users experience difficulties in the process of geospatial analysis and take the initiative to guide or assist the user with proper actions [14, 5]. We define users as those who are experts in a particular problem domain but are novices in the tool domain related to GISystems [15]. They are without or with only a little knowledge of geography or GIScience [20]. We develop a conceptual framework that characterizes the cooperative and helpful behavior of machine guidance during a spatial analytical process at 1) the problem-solving level, 2) the strategy level (when the user is constructing solutions), and 3) the operational level. This framework is used to infer the kinds of knowledge representation and reasoning capability that are necessary for a practical machine guidance system.

We apply a human-centered design approach [6] for developing and evaluating the prototype machine guidance to answer the research questions that **1) when guidance is needed, and 2) how guidance should be provided** (e.g. in what ways and to what degrees) to maintain a productive analytic process. We start by identifying design opportunities through modeling users' analytical tasks and cognitive activities. Then, we generate guidance strategies and design ideas for each of the design opportunities. The physical design of machine guidance will be evaluated and refined through controlled lab experiments to assess the effectiveness of alternative guidance strategies. We expect multiple findings from such experiments that can inform design principles on what degree the guidance contents should be provided at a suitable time based on participants' feedback and responses.

Our work conceptualizes machine guidance design in the GIScience domain regarding when and how machine guidance should be built. It is supported by findings based on the empirical

study regarding what are the actual cognitive difficulties when doing geospatial analysis and at which stages help is needed. A better understanding of when and how guidance should be designed contributes to the development of a science of design for machine guidance. It can fill the gap that there is a lack of understanding of the machine guidance behaviors in facilitating geospatial analysis.

2 Overall Approach

Users of the GIS applications are no longer restricted to the GIS experts but a wider range of users with expertise in specific domains [19]. However, there is a divide between the targeted users who are the geo-computing experts and the real users who do not have the expertise of the current GIS software [21]. In our proposal, we define the target users of the machine guidance as those who have occasional needs to conduct geospatial analytical tasks based on their own domain interests and expertise. This group of users are experts in a particular problem domain but are novices in the tool domain related to GIS systems [15]. They are without or with only a little knowledge of geography or GIS science in general [20]. More importantly, they have a goal of doing geospatial analysis for critical decision-making.

We propose a mixed-initiative *knowledge-based* [8] machine guidance [4]. Using a human-centered design (HCD) approach [6], we start by understanding users' cognitive difficulties to determine when guidance is needed. The major aim of the step is to form a concrete design rationale [2]. Given a specific analytical goal, a series of tasks should be completed when a practical problem-solving strategy is formed. We assume that guidance should be provided if there are a lot of cognitive activities going on. Too much cognitive load may hinder the analyst from making progress when doing each task [3]. We enumerate the major tasks when doing geospatial analysis and modeling the anticipated user behaviors as a starting point. The model is of two layers. The task layer indicates the basic tasks to accomplish. Above the task level, a cognitive layer is attached to each task reflecting the relevant thinking process.

After knowing what to solve or when to introduce the guidance, we take the following steps to decide the practical design strategies. It leads to another essential question that *how to provide guidance*. Design strategy and guidance contents vary depending on the different natures of the cognitive challenges. Through the ideation process, detailed design ideas and requirements can be generated.

Naturally, the design ideas will be implemented into a prototype machine guidance. Given a spatial analytical task, the system needs to identify what is missing in forming an executable plan so that guidance will be generated. The generated guidance will be presented to users and guide them to make critical decisions in order to complete the analysis. Especially, interactions between the user and the guidance system are essential for forming a "shared plan" [12, 17] based on both the user's perception and judgments as well as the knowledge and reasoning capability of the system. It is inspired by the process that how human beings form feasible plans when working towards a goal. If the system can be designed and implemented in a way that it is able to closely resemble the ways people reason about the space and the problem, it can be applied as an assistance rather than requiring the users to adapt themselves to the machine [11].

2.1 When to Provide Guidance

Machine guidance should be introduced at the right time, especially **when analysts are facing cognitive difficulties**. Our machine guidance in supporting geospatial analysis should take place to help the human analyst at different analytical stages [16]. As to the

question “when the guidance is needed,” we assume that timely guidance should be provided when analysts face difficulties that hinder their analytical process. Specifically, the analyst usually encounter a huge cognitive load when figuring out the right solution in order to resume the analytical process.

2.2 How to Provide Guidance

Design strategies are formed **based on the nature of the cognitive difficulties** that are identified. For instance, one may not be able to continue the analysis because 1) not knowing what are the available solutions or strategies given an analytical goal; 2) a wrong strategy was chosen thus wrong actions were performed; 3) a right strategy was used but met a challenge in performing the right action e.g. finding and using the right tool; 4) a wrong goal was set in the problem domain at the very beginning. Then, guidance that is in different formats and degrees can be designed based on the unique nature of each difficulty that is identified.

3 Empirical Study

To answer the major research questions, our research plan is based on formative evaluation strategies [18]. We already got the IRB approval to analyze what are undergraduate students’ cognitive difficulties when conducting risk management tasks using ArcMap. This study has two major objectives. First, we will find out when cognitive difficulties occur when students are conducting geospatial analysis. Second, we will explore the nature of these cognitive difficulties and a range of possible guiding strategies to help the students.

To achieve the objectives, we will conduct an ethnographic study to observe students solving problems using geospatial analysis in classrooms and what are the common mistakes made in their deliverables (e.g. assignment and exam answers). We identify the undergraduate students who registered for the course SRA 468 (Geospatial Analysis of Risk) as our major participants. It is a required senior-level course for undergraduate students majoring in Security and Risk Analysis (SRA Major). It is designed to prepare the students to conduct geospatial analysis in risk management contexts. Students in this class represent our visioned users of machine guidance. They represent a large group of people who 1) are out of the geography or GIS domain, and 2) need to conduct geospatial analysis to solve problems in their own fields e.g. risk management and analysis.

Students in the course are senior students who have already taken a series of courses. The SRA major has a requirement of 16 prescribed courses. These courses cover the basic introductory contents regarding security and risk analysis as well as critical decision-making in socioeconomic and legal domains (see detailed course requirements from ¹). It is also accompanied with courses that teach practical analytical skills like writing, programming, data management and visualization. After three years of training and education, we believe that the students can be regarded as experienced in the risk management domain based on three years of accumulation of training and education.

In the study, we will give participants a spatial analytical project to finish in a classroom environment. We are going to observe and take notes about participants’ difficulties and how their problems are addressed. We will have follow-up interviews with the students in order

¹ <https://bulletins.psu.edu/undergraduate/colleges/information-sciences-technology/security-risk-analysis-bs/#programrequirements>

to get verification and clarification on the real difficulties they met. It is designed to capture internal information like their mental thoughts that can not be captured via observation.

The collected data (including the observatory notes, task responses, and interview responses) will be coded using an analytic framework. The data will be analyzed to form a systematic understanding of the cognitive challenges encountered by students and how they leverage the instructor's guidance during geospatial analyses. Our method of generating such understanding is through testing a set of pre-defined hypotheses. These hypotheses were established by synthesizing literature from spatial analysis and spatial cognition:

- When doing geospatial analysis, which is a human reasoning process, guidance should be introduced at different analytical stages [13]:
 - S1: Understanding the phenomenon and finding the data
 - S2: Choosing executable solution and workflow
 - S3: Conducting operations
 - S4: Evaluating the outputs and final results

We will use the hypotheses as a major lens when analyzing and coding the collected data in order to fulfill our major research objectives. In this case, the perceived difficulties and guidance strategies will be categorized based on their nature so that we can understand at which stages (when) difficulties occur and how a guidance strategy can be provided.

4 Conclusion

To the best of our knowledge, our work is a very first trial and attempt to introduce machine guidance to boost the current GISystems and potentially advance the broader field of GIScience. This initial work serves as a proof of concept, demonstrating the concept of machine guidance, its fundamental structures, and its potential significance.

Our ongoing research is dedicated to evaluating and refining guidance strategies for practical applicability. Understanding human analysts' real cognitive challenges as well as their nature is a critical step. It informs us when guidance is needed and what guidance strategies should be embedded into the guidance system. We will focus on the empirical study as well as the guidance evaluation process. Major findings concluded from observation and in-depth conversations are considered critical feedback so the design approach can be further revised and improved.

Our aim is to spark discourse and scholarly inquiry into the discussion and research regarding the machine guidance approach in facilitating geospatial analysis both academically and socially. We hope that our efforts can inspire further research and encourage innovations in the development of alternative design and implementation frameworks.

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